

“To Fathom Hell or Soar Angelic”: Theorizing a Psychedelic Politics

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Abstract: Amidst a heyday of overlapping crises, political subjects are encouraged to pursue economic and political freedom through individual effort, amidst illusions of collectivity in digital spaces. From these logics of alienation, transhumanist solutions to these crises have gained increased traction, even striving to liberate us from the anxieties of impermanence and mortality. I note that these disturbing, apolitical developments have emerged from liberal conceptions of political imagination—as a boundary-breaking expression of human will. I posit that recovering imagination, as a faculty of political judgment, requires transformative, transcendental experiences that reclaim the free play of our cognitive faculties and rupture our ingrained habits of thinking and being. To that end, I articulate and argue for a psychedelic politics that begins as individual self-work, and manifests as collectively rooted political action. By willfully breaking away from the familiar, we can imagine alternative political worlds and collectively act to bring them forth, through the lessons that remain with us after a transcendent experience.

Keywords: psychedelics, transhumanism, aesthetics, sublime, imagination, judgment

In today’s political world, we face a unique crisis of mass alienation, or a mass retreat from public and social life in order to focus on individualistic concerns and the pursuit of immediate gratification.¹ This crisis has been brought on by several interrelated factors: the isolation and lingering psychic harms of the (ongoing) COVID-19 pandemic; the despair of an ever-worsening ecological crisis; and the transfer of social, public spheres of activity and community from physical to digital spaces. The dominance of social media and technology today is especially important, as said technologies are often heralded as new frontiers of social and political action. The consolidation of political power amid Silicon Valley and the billionaire class has dovetailed with an increased fervor for techno-optimism, with heavy financial investment in developing technologies from the realms of science fiction (and heedless of the social critiques embedded in the genre).

This techno-optimism is distinctly transhumanist in nature, in that the promises of liberation offered are grounded in an escape from the human condition. Proponents of artificial intelligence promise liberation from the drudgery of mundane labor, as well as the effort of artistic expression and creation. Other transhumanists offer visions of virtual societies, in pursuit of a future in which people can freely augment their bodies with cybernetic enhancements, separate their consciousnesses from their bodies and inhabit digital spaces, and theoretically escape the shackles of mortality itself.² Such is the final goal of an ideology of domination that is founded on the ideals of a sovereign self that is master over all of nature. Transhumanist visions of technology become the path to human salvation, ironically by robbing us of what it means to be human—from the joys of sensory experience to the realms of spontaneity and possibility.³

My paper develops an account of contemplative, imaginative political practice that seeks to counter this mass alienation, and recover attachments towards our embodiment and the lifeworlds we collectively inhabit. This contemplative practice calls for channeling the body's innate capability to freely alter our perceptions and cultivate radical political imaginations. Specifically, I argue that there is a political, therapeutic benefit to guided, internal introspection through mindfulness practices—particularly the use of psychedelics. When engaged purposefully, psychedelics can not only help us alter our ways of thinking and being, but also allow us to recover a sense of wonder and awe that is difficult to cultivate amidst a life of familiar routines and existential anxieties. Such experiences (or “trips”) possess an affective intensity that sets the stage for the free play of our imaginative faculties, which in turn lays the groundwork for profound shifts in how we perceive and live in the world.

Such an intense transcendent experience can be disquieting and unsettling, but it can also resonate with profound joy and elation. It taps into the same liberatory “escapism” that transhumanism promotes, while also grounding us in the world—resisting the disembodied, immortal vision of a “human” future that many technocrats uphold as a utopian possibility. While a positive outcome from such experiences cannot be guaranteed for every individual and caution must be exercised, the publicly perceived negative outcomes of psychedelic use are largely derived from stigmatization and have little basis in fact. These agentic forces interact with our nervous systems to forge new neural pathways, and accounts from users of psychedelic therapy reveal the remarkable potential our bodies possess to change the way we see the world and our place in it. Most importantly, these transformative insights and shifts in thought and behavior last long after the “trip” has ended. By engaging with our own bodies, cognitive processes, and habits (whether embodied or externally enforced), we can recover an affective attachment to living in the world (with all the vulnerability that living entails) rather than escaping it, and strive to forge a brighter future.

In the next section of this paper, I discuss the escapist, Promethean logics of transhumanism to demonstrate that: 1) transhumanism is a response to the crises of neoliberal capitalism, and 2) that the logics of transhumanism are

rooted in anxieties surrounding mortality and impermanence. I then turn to the role of imagination in driving political judgment and action, and argue that democratic readings of political imagination as a means of realizing freedom have been appropriated by and sustain transhumanist visions of our future. However, I also argue that recapturing political imagination, and tapping into affectively charged aesthetic experiences (via the sublime), provide us with a mechanism to stretch and transform our imaginations. I then articulate and defend a model of psychedelic politics as a means of facilitating this transformative experience, and conclude with some insights as to how a psychedelic politics could be harnessed as a driver of collective action.

TRANSHUMANISM: ESCAPING SOCIALITY, POLITICS, AND MORTALITY

The current state of civil society is one of domination by neoliberal capitalism, which exacerbates ecological collapse, dismantles commonly shared spaces and democratic ideals, and intensifies xenophobic conflicts between political subjects in order to draw their ire away from the entrenched billionaire class. The ever-growing tech industry, while not responsible for the roots of liberalism's crises, has greatly intensified this malignancy; server farms and data processing plants for the development of AI and cryptocurrencies have a massive environmental impact, while social media pervades and polarizes political discourse. The technologies of transhumanism, produced by liberal capitalism, then offer themselves as mechanisms for achieving freedom. These solutions range from small-scale interventions in daily working life (such as the use of generative AI to "streamline" productivity), to attempts to realize visions from science fiction (the transference of consciousness to virtual spaces).

However, it would be a mistake to lay the crises of liberal capitalism solely at the feet of transhumanists. Transhumanism is simply an extension of the ideologies of domination that underlie liberalism (and much of the Western tradition), via an emphasis on the enhancement of the individual subject in order to transcend the boundaries of mental capability, embodiment, and mortality.⁴ These logics of enhancement and individual attainment reverberate through liberal capitalism, profoundly limiting our ability to imagine alternative, more collective modes of life. As Jodi Dean notes in her foundational work on solidarity, liberalism's political structure is built on an "individualist lens of competitive self-assertion" that limits the potential for a "hopeful we." In the place of collective solidarity, liberal politics offers us a mere series of fragmented moments in history where "egocentric interests" briefly unite in fragile alliances.⁵

This individuation of political subjects imposes an impossible ideal, where the self-sufficient, autonomous, and free individual is little more than a fictional character in a grand narrative. Today, this manifests itself in an economy of "flexible" gig work, where a lack of insurance and long-term financial benefits is framed as freedom from dependence on others. The loan-burdened college

student, laid-off middle manager, and former retiree find “freedom” through personal vehicle ownership and rotation between rideshare and food delivery gigs, at the mercy of a dispassionate rating algorithm and local ordinances (funded and fought for by tech conglomerates) that deny their status as workers deserving benefits and support. The myth of the self-sufficient individual promotes an inward, focused drive for flexibility and the promise of success, all to mask the emotional pain of alienation and an ego-centric drive to politics that even left-wing organizations struggle to overcome.⁶

This crisis of individuation has been greatly exacerbated by transhumanism, and while many creators of digital technologies may not subscribe to that label, they are incentivized to draw as much of our time and attention into digital spaces as possible. During the early days of the pandemic, when stay-at-home orders went into effect across the country, technologies like Zoom and Twitch became immensely popular as means of recovering some semblance of social, collective life. Beyond the pandemic, social media has presented itself as a viable career avenue for those who are discontented with their jobs, or who simply want to try and make money doing “what they love”—all while inundating users with examples of successful travel and food Instagram bloggers, or high-profile Twitch streamers turning their passion for video games or art into profit. The alienation of the individual under liberal capitalism, maintained by the mythical presentation of the Tesla-owning Uber driver or high-tech Twitch streamer, create false visions of self-ownership and social collectivity that foster anxiety, depression, and a desperate longing for connection through a digital economy of likes and retweets. The cycle of profit disguised as liberation continues as alienated individuals are encouraged to alleviate their loneliness through consumption and immediate gratification.⁷ As tech corporations acquire more political power and influence, they have developed liberatory solutions to the political and economic crises of their own making.

Some of these solutions are rooted in Promethean techno-optimism, such as investment in generative AI. AI is often framed as a transformative application with limitless potential to revolutionize human labor by automating repetitive drudgery or by “learning” the most optimal methods to reach certain outcomes (i.e., patient outcomes in healthcare or likely successful investments in venture capitalism) or to eliminate the time and labor required for creative and intellectual expression.⁸ Rather than utilizing AI to automate the “robotic” functions of human labor, the tech industry seems more interested in eliminating the time and “effort” of creative and intellectual expression, replacing it with something entirely lacking in authenticity and intentionality.⁹ However, other applications of AI move beyond techno-optimism and into the realm of pure escapism in the form of virtual reality. Film studios have utilized AI to recreate the likenesses of deceased actors, and many proponents of AI envision a future where we can recreate and interact with the minds of our deceased loved ones. Many transhumanists go further to advocate for simulated realities that we can freely enter by separating (or emulating) our conscious selves—“liberating” us from the shackles of embodiment.¹⁰ This vision of a disembodied humanity is

promoted in the name of alleviating human suffering, escaping the pain of death, and maximizing our potential (with the worry of exacerbating systemic inequalities haphazardly waved away with a mandate for “good public policy”).¹¹ However, even if this transhumanist vision was feasible, it would come at the cost of the physical elements of our embodiment that bring joy to our existence. The joys of taste, sound, and touch as we know them would be lost to us—either replaced synthetically or deemed unnecessary functions.

What unites these “transformative” technologies, beyond increased attention and funding from billionaires, is an underlying anxiety surrounding death and the pursuit of immortality. James Rowe argues that death anxieties underlie liberalism’s attachments to individualism and humanity’s “cosmic specialness,” and western socio-political structures facilitate these “fantasies of supremacy that compensate for the belittlement” that arrives inevitably with death.¹² This “will to supremacy” emerges from a “chronic existential unease”—an uncomfortably familiar sensation in today’s political world.¹³ Joshua Hurtado sees this as an inherent function of continually evolving “techno-capitalism,” which seems to expand its frontiers of commodification beyond the boundaries of death.¹⁴ As Hurtado and others rightly note, this pursuit of immortality (if realized) would only further worsen the crisis of alienation, as only those with sufficient wealth or political power would likely be able to access technologies that replicate their consciousness in virtual spaces.¹⁵ Though such technological “solutions” may sound too close to the realms of speculative science fiction to be considered a pressing political issue (and are highly unlikely to be fully realized), the transhumanist pursuit of immortality is likely to continue accumulating capital at the expense of addressing social problems today.

The crises of an isolating pandemic and late capitalism have only exacerbated the symptoms of liberalism’s cancerous emphasis on individual sovereignty over fellowship with human and non-human others. From the political imaginaries emerging from these crises, transhumanism materializes and offers transformative, seemingly utopian visions of an immortal, disembodied future—the ultimate alleviation of suffering. Yet even among critics of these imaginaries, anxieties over death linger. As Hurtado reveals with his defense of “alternative” imaginaries of immortality, our politics struggles to accept a vision of living well that embraces death, and the hope of leaving a better world for those who may follow.¹⁶ In the next section of this paper, I take up the role of imagination in the liberal political tradition and note that while the concept is generative, it also facilitates the logics of supremacy that drive transhumanism. I then introduce alternative conceptions of political imagination that emphasize humility, collectivity, and rupture from habituated ways of thinking, before turning to the potential of psychedelics and other mindfulness practices as a means of cultivating this alternative imaginary.

IMAGINATION, SENSATION, AND TRANSFORMATION

Perhaps the most famous work on imagination in political thought comes from Hannah Arendt's posthumously published notes on Immanuel Kant's *Critique of Judgment*, in which imagination is an essential faculty that is employed in the process of judgment formation. For Arendt, imagination is "the ability to make present what is absent" and to engage in judgments based on our representation of objects we have encountered (or sensed).¹⁷ Through the process of judgment, we form an understanding of the world through sensory stimuli and lived experiences. It is the cognitive process that allows us to develop conceptual knowledge and develop a narrative (or tell stories, in Arendt's language) about the world and our place in it. In Immanuel Kant's conceptualization of judgment, imagination plays a critical role. It emerges when our judgments are unable to produce new knowledge—essentially running up against the barriers of what we already know and understand about the world. In these moments of internal contestation, our imagination overcomes these barriers through the "free play of our cognitive faculties."¹⁸ This concept is perhaps best illuminated by Linda Zerilli, who writes: In the "free play of the faculties". . . imagination in particular is no longer bound to the logic of recognition, which requires that it reproduce absent objects in accordance with the concept-governed linear temporality of the understanding. Imagination. . . is not bound to the law of causality, but is productive and spontaneous, not merely reproductive of what is already known, but generative of new forms and figures.¹⁹

My purpose in extricating imagination and judgment is not to intervene in the large body of extant literature on this topic, or to illuminate the particular tensions and contradictions that have been exhaustively debated.²⁰ Rather, I want to identify how this vision of political imagination, as the realization of human freedom and action, has been appropriated by liberal capitalism and transhumanism in their visions of self-realization and utopian progress. To make this link, it is helpful to identify commonalities shared across various interpretations of political imagination. Firstly, that imagination reaches its fullest potential when liberated from practical or cognitive restraints, allowing us to envision possibilities beyond what we have previously experienced in life.²¹ Secondly, that the productive and spontaneous character of political imagination enables the subject to channel their experiences into formulating an imaginative vision of the future, and then undertake actions to realize that future. There is an affective dimension to imagination, such as joy at realizing new possibilities or inadequacy in comparing one's own position to that of another, which is representative of "the subject's purposive anticipation of the future or the 'feeling of life.'"²² To synthesize these points, imagination enables us to formulate a vision of the future, and the power of human reason and will drives us to bring our imagined futures into existence.²³

This vision of political imagination does not preclude any unified set of goals for the kind of imagined future each of us might wish to realize. As Arendt argues, discourse is a vital element of this political process, so that shared goals across diverse constituencies can be identified.²⁴ Avshalom Schwartz challenges

political imagination's potential to forge new collectives merely through discourse, arguing that it supports incompatible visions of civil society. On one side of the divide, "constitutive" political imagination supports the background operations of civil society, such as the ideals of common sense and shared beliefs that provide a moral order.²⁵ For example, theoretical visions of civil society emphasizing the legitimacy and order of the state as an entity shaping the character of its citizens utilize this form of imagination to foster a kind of restrictive mythos. In a somewhat contradictory fashion, this conservative iteration of political imagination sets limits on what elements of society can be questioned, and what alternatives can be imagined.²⁶ The other side of the divide, termed "creative" or "critical" political imagination, illustrates the innovative element of imagination. This form of political imagination pushes boundaries, ruptures habits, and works to realize alternatives to the status quo in civil society.²⁷ Schwartz argues—correctly, in my view—that there are limits as to how far political imagination can go in effecting radical political change (at least following the typology above). On the surface, it is easy to see the constitutive form of political imagination as one enforcing a hierarchical structure in order to maintain the legitimacy and order of the state, without going as far as to take the form of a particular ideology. Schwartz draws on Plato's mythos employed to strengthen the longevity of the state, such as the allegory of the cave and other myths used to shape the character of citizens in *The Republic*.²⁸ A progressive position can thus read constitutive political imagination as "regressive" or hostile to innovation, while the "creative" form works to realize transformative good.

However, this misses how both liberal capitalism and trans-humanism have appropriated political imagination as a boundary-breaking expression of human will in order to simultaneously 1) reinforce the dominant socio-economic status quo, and 2) facilitate the "progressive" improvement of life for the dominant group within society. Consider our earlier examples of the "flexible" gig economy worker today—bombarded by images of "successful" entrepreneurs who realized the "good life" by pursuing self-employment and monetizing their personal interests and hobbies. The constitutive imagination of liberal capitalism is one that utilizes such myths in order to sustain itself, offering false promises of freedom through individualism. As a result, constitutive political imagination does not foster a collective political will so much as fractures it, rendering the political realm a world of performative spectacles.²⁹

The creative political imagination, on the other hand, does not originate from the polis but from the elites that shape society to their ideals. The role of the human will as a means of enacting innovative change is the core faculty in this process—capable of and naturally driven towards the breaking of boundaries. As Schwartz notes, the will is not a collectively enacted faculty, but rather is the life activity of the "individual artist, thinker, visionary, or social entrepreneur, who are able to detach themselves from their society's constitutive imagination and transcend its limits."³⁰ Creative political imagination is seemingly apolitical, as the collective is only influenced by the visions of the eccentric genius and

plays little role in determining which innovations to pursue. This is the driver of transhumanist ideology: visions of a possible future humanity drawn from the realms of science fiction and relentlessly pursued according to the will of techno-optimists and billionaires. Whether these visions are actually realized is somewhat irrelevant as long as profits are generated; consequences manifest as these Promethean goals take hold in and reshape the public imagination, convincing their adherents that “genius” billionaires are working in pursuit of the greater good.

Our first goal should be to reclaim the imagination as a driver of political transformation and action, driven by collective engagement rather than the whims of a sheer minority who would rather be labeled as inherent geniuses than go through the humbling work of learning. A collectively rooted vision of imagination can tap into the transformative potential of Schwartz’s creative variant, and perhaps even channel some of the escapism we see in transhumanism, albeit temporarily. Fundamentally, we might ask how imagination can elicit a sense of awe and wonder, while decentering the self and assumptions of mastery over the world around us.³¹ Many of us have likely had experiences that tap into these affective sensations, perhaps even in collective settings that call attention to one another in those moments of affective intensity. For example, those who have participated in religious services might recall a sense of spiritual elevation and togetherness during collective song and worship—a sense that “God is in the room.” The moment when judgment reaches a level of affective intensity that stretches the imagination to its limits, potentially transforming the subject’s disposition, is known as the sublime. Foundational philosophical work on the sublime, from the ancient narrative of Longinus to the US environmental conservation movement of the nineteenth century, provides a range of varied accounts of the aesthetic experience. A unified description of the sublime identifies it as a function of our imagination, driven to a level of intensity by a provocation to our sensory experience. In most accounts, the source of this provocation is a dynamic, overwhelming presentation of nature external to the viewing subject. Nature presents itself to the subject with dynamic or seemingly infinite characteristics—such as the roaring expanse of the ocean, and the feeling of insignificance we might experience standing along the shore. As Kant asserts, aesthetic experience is rooted in the interaction between “a ground external to ourselves” and the affective responses that manifest within the viewing subject and projected (or “introduced” in Kant’s language) onto external nature.³² For this project, the critical element of the sublime unifies the imagination, our embodied perceptive and sensory capabilities, and the potential for transformative shifts in how we see the world and our place in it. This transformative potential is realized through a challenge to the subject’s rational, cognitive faculties that results in awe, anxiety, and terror.³³ Edmund Burke offers a materialist conception of the imagination, where our judgments are stimulated through physical stimuli—some tastes and smells evoke a sense of revulsion, while a simple act of intimate touch in some areas of the body can provoke an almost overwhelming sense of joy that is

notably separate from our typical “rational” faculties. The sublime takes this affective intensity to a level that almost threatens the subject. As Burke writes, “The passion caused by the great and sublime in nature, when those causes operate most powerfully is Astonishment, and astonishment is that state of the soul in which all its motions are suspended, with some degree of horror. . . the inferior effects are admiration, reverence, and respect.”³⁴ Burke effectively gives us a causal mechanism where sensory stimuli evokes psychological shifts in our disposition. At a certain level of affective intensity, the fear we may feel in response to threats to our existence is mixed with an awe and reverence that helps us reorient ourselves in relation to the world.

However, the critical element of sublimity is not the specific presentation of the objects that spark such an encounter, but rather our “profound and violent affective response” to the sublime, and the resulting “mode of thinking or sensing that is radically different from our usual ways of thinking and sensing.”³⁵ The goal of such a project is to “reflect on the limits and conditions of our experience,” so that we might attempt to transgress those limits through the power of imagination.³⁶ Through this transformative potential, the sublime gives us a mechanism for recovering a creative political imagination from the individuating forces it sustains.

The task before us now is to conceive of political practices that can rupture this ingrained habitus (whether we are willing or not) to unsettle the individual ego, encourage us to live in and experience the world to which we are bound, and most importantly, to preserve it for generations of humans and non-humans alike to flourish long after we become dust. Jeremy Bendik-Keymer argues that contemplative, intentional individual “self work” is necessary to rebuild our capacities for wonder, and this is a necessary goal if we are “to become right in one’s moral relations” in a tumultuous era of crisis.³⁷ From this premise, the next section of this paper argues for imaginative self-work in the form of a psychedelic politics.

RUPTURE, DISCOMFORT, AND HEALING: THEORIZING A PSYCHEDELIC POLITICS

We can conceptualize the starting point of a psychedelic politics as an individual, purposive act of self-exploration to expand our patterns of thought—or in Arendt’s language, to “train one’s imagination to go visiting.”³⁸ Donna Haraway also draws on the metaphor of “going visiting,” emphasizing the “wild virtue of curiosity” necessary for engaging in such a reflective practice to “lead its practitioners a bit too far off the path” and to tell stories.³⁹ The turn I make with this practice is to, rather than “go visit” the imagined position of another or to a site of external aesthetic experience, to turn inward to explore our own consciousness and adopt an alternative lens through which we can behold the world. It is a form of imaginative practice that guides the subject through an inner space that, in the heyday of overlapping crises, can be difficult for political subjects to traverse. John Dewey argues that the enemy of aesthetic experience

is the “humdrum” or “submission to convention in practice and intellectual procedure.”⁴⁰ Liberating ourselves from the restrictions of long-held rigid patterns of thought (especially those that have been structurally enforced and internalized, such as addiction), can lead us to apprehend and attend to the world in novel ways.⁴¹

Although this particular example may not appeal to some, I focus on psilocybin (and similar psychedelics) in this section for two key reasons. Firstly, in order to destigmatize the recreational or therapeutic use of psilocybin, which in recent years has gained traction in neuro- science research as a possible treatment for depression (especially in cases related to terminal illness), anxiety, and tobacco/alcohol addic- tion—coupled with decriminalization efforts in municipalities across the United States. As Michael Pollan notes in his exploration of the history of psychedelics, they were treated as a legitimate means of therapeutic treatment in the 1950s-‘70s, before being stigmatized as a sign of social immorality by the Nixon and Reagan administrations.⁴²

Secondly, and more importantly, the experience of ingesting psilo- cybin prompts affective, sensorial responses that lead to moments of rupture in our habituated ways of thinking and being. The transition from one state of cognition (or being), to a different, augmented or inhibited state of cognition is an affective experience that is intensity felt within the body. Brian Massumi demonstrates that these affec- tive moments of transition alter our perceptions, and those shifts in perception leave memory-like experiences that the body can recall and learn from after the altered state has ended.⁴³ Psychedelics func- tion in this exact manner by galvanizing pyramidal neural receptors in our brain to augment connectivity between neurons in the frontal cortex: the area of the brain that controls executive functions, organi- zational skills, memory, emotional regulation, and social interaction. These neural receptors, through interaction with thalamus (the central node in the brain that processes sensory information), allow us to form judgments based on our physical, embodied experiences. These new neural pathways streamline and strengthen communication between the networks of our nervous system, leading to a fundamental shift in our perception.⁴⁴ As I discuss below, the important element of a psychedelic politics does not occur during the trip itself, but in the lasting changes in how we relate to ourselves and to one another.

Such a transformation of our imaginations begins with a shift in our perception, which initially can lead to what Julia Kristeva identi- fies as a “spasmodic” affective response, when aesthetic experiences may discomfort or overwhelm us through physical and emotional sensation. Or, to draw on Deleuze’s terminology, by disrupting the “rhythm” or “variable repetition or pulsation” undergirding all senso- rial experience. Shifts in the rhythm, or a “chaotic arrhythmia,” disori- ents the syntheses upon which the subject engages with the external world.⁴⁵ Consider a commonplace example of this phenomenon: the manifestation of physical symptoms brought about by anxiety. An anxiety attack may be brought about through a visual stimulus that represents a threat to our

security, or through an internal sense of despair; such circumstances are certainly familiar to those who have attempted to navigate the overlapping crises of our current political moment. In these moments of crisis, a chaotic arrhythmia destabilizes our resting heart rate, our breathing becomes shallow, and we become hyper-focused on an impending sense of despair. For some, these periods of anxiety alter our perceptions of self and reality so drastically that we feel as though we are on the verge of death itself. In turn, our bodies magnify minor sensations in our skin, GI tracts, breathing, and minds—even generating chest pain that can mimic a heart attack. During a psychedelic experience, a similarly uncomfortable sensation emerges when the subject struggles to represent the unrepresentable, such as the mental task of grappling with changes in visual perception and undulating bodily sensations. The subject may feel a sense of abjection as the body's neural receptors in the brain and GI tract interact with the freshly processed psilocybin, generating a rush of serotonin. The outset of this journey and the abjection felt in the body can often provoke feelings of anxiety and uncertainty, as the subject grapples with the ongoing shift in their perception. As the psilocybin forges neural connections, the subject's heart rate can increase, the pupils begin to dilate, and our vision begins to change—new connections, patterns, and forms of life become apparent to us. The lines between subject and object become increasingly blurred, and a feeling of overwhelming abjection and uncertainty “takes the ego back to its source”—discomfortingly but temporarily losing one's sense of self.⁴⁶

The initial moments of a psychedelic experience demonstrate the affective power of the “a body engulfed by a chaotic profusion of sensations at different levels of intensities.”⁴⁷ This intensity is part of aesthetic experience, as John Dewey reminds us, somewhat presciently writing before the advent of psychedelics in the United States and describing their effects with surprising accuracy. Being receptive to shifts in our perception and ways of thinking requires an act of “surrender... through a controlled activity that may well be intense.”⁴⁸ He continues that “in much of our intercourse with our surroundings we withdraw; sometimes from fear... sometimes from preoccupation with other matters... To steep ourselves in a subject-matter we have first to plunge into it... We must summon energy and pitch it at a responsive key in order to take in.”⁴⁹ Michael Halewood, in a provocative reading of Whitehead relating to psychedelics, sees these cognitive shifts as an intensification of human experience.⁵⁰ The anxiety and elation of our lived experience is brought to the forefront of our minds (as I discuss below in relation to psychedelic therapy) in a manner that reintroduces our conscious and unconscious selves, stripping away veneers of social masking and repression in a violent act of truth-telling. Rather than allowing us to hallucinate some alternate reality, the psychedelic experience is a way for the world to “pro-suppose” itself to us, rendering our souls visible.⁵¹

This experience can be uncomfortable and jarring in its initial stages, but it is only the beginning of the psychedelic “come-up.” Brian Massumi notes that affectively charged, embodied forces (using the language of abduction) provoke

anxiety and awe, but also lay the groundwork for a sense of freedom and vitality to emerge. The expansion of the subject's horizons encourages new ways of thinking, sensing, and living amidst weirdness, imperfection, interconnection, and joy.⁵² Kant discusses the aesthetic intensity of the sublime in a similar fashion, where a sensorial experience overwhelms the subject's cognitive faculties to provoke anxiety and terror, before giving way to "a delight in an extension affecting the imagination itself."⁵³ In essence, we must allow ourselves to be open to the experience in order to avoid passively allowing ourselves to be overwhelmed by it. Abjection and physical discomfort can then be called out and recognized for what they are, and how they operate in our minds. This acceptance then gives way to a disquieting, surreal source of joy as we "plateau" (or the effects of the psilocybin reach their peak and the mind adjusts): We might be emotionally moved as we become lost in the sound of a symphony, or in the rushing waves of the ocean, or even through something as simple as experiencing prolonged physical and emotional intimacy with one another. We might feel as though we are "losing ourselves" in those moments, and find joy in that dissolution.

In his interviews of both licensed and "underground" psychedelic therapists, Michael Pollan notes that a goal of the therapeutic practice is to unsettle the ego, or "our addiction to a pattern of thinking with the self at the center of it."⁵⁴ Indeed, this is a habit that we are often discouraged to break by a political and economic system that emphasizes individual freedom and productivity above communal solidarity. Breaking away from this ingrained habitus is a challenging task even for those of us who grapple with the political injustices as academics and activists, as we are not immune from the distractions of the information economy or the demands of daily life. Taking the time to engage in what James Rowe calls "radical mindfulness" practices is both an act of political resistance and care, as we reclaim time for contemplation and self-work.⁵⁵ While the dissolution of ego might seem like a terrifying prospect, it can also liberate us from the anxieties of impermanence and mortality.⁵⁶

Pollan also interviewed numerous patients of psychedelic therapy to identify the short- and long-term benefits that they experienced. Some patients experienced pleasant epiphanies to take better care of their health and establish new routines; some felt a spiritual elevation from taking a simple short walk outside; some realized with a mix of joy and sorrow that they were no longer committed to a faltering relationship; some overcame far deeper struggles with addiction and suicidal idealization. Responses to aesthetic experiences of this intensity, like our imagination's response to the sublime, are not predetermined or universal. Some effects may be short-term, while others grapple with healing more severe traumas and deeply ingrained patterns of thinking. Below are some notes from recovering addicts who took psychedelic therapy, and how they describe the lasting, beneficial changes they noticed in their lives six months after their experience:

I saw my children and I was bawling and bawling, for the life they never had... I saw Jesus on the cross. It was just his head and shoulders, and it was like I was a little kid in a tiny helicopter circling around his head... And he just sort of gathered me up in his hands, you know, the way you would comfort a small child. I felt such a great weight lift from my shoulders, felt very much at peace.⁵⁷

A veil dropped from my eyes, things were suddenly clear, glowing, bright. I looked at plants and felt their beauty. I can still look at my orchids and feel that: that is one thing that has really lasted. ⁵⁸

Normally, when Dad [an abuser] comes up in my head, I just push the thought away. But this time I went the other way... I looked him in the eye. That was a really big thing for me, to literally face the demon. And there he was. But he was a horse! A military horse standing on its hind legs, dressed in a military outfit with a helmet, and holding a gun. It was terrifying, and I wanted to push the image aside, but I didn't. Instead I looked the horse in the eyes—and promptly started to laugh. That's when a really bad trip turned... I had this overwhelming feeling of deep contentment... The insights I gained during the trial have never left and will never leave me.⁵⁹

Although research on the psychological impacts of psilocybin is limited due to federally mandated restrictions, experimental studies have found that subjects return from their “trip” with a heightened sense of inner peace and self-awareness, heightened optimism, decreased anxiety, and—most importantly—a heightened sense of interpersonal connectivity and compassion, a willingness to express positive emotions, and a drive to pursue unactualized possibilities.⁶⁰ In another recent clinical study, researchers found an overview effect where the “ego dissolution experienced during a participant’s ‘most intense’ psychedelic experience positively predicted liberal political views, openness and nature-relatedness, and negatively predicted authoritarian political views.”⁶¹ In both cited studies, post-intervention interviews conducted at six months and two years after the “trip” found that the results did not diminish with time—which brings us to a critical point.

Few other experiences can set the stage for the free play of our cognitive faculties (which Kant reminds us is essential in the process of judgment formation), and can so positively result lead the subject to cultivate novel and imaginative perceptions.⁶² Yet there are also tensions and injustices that can emerge within a psychedelic politics that we must attend to. As Arun Saldanha notes, the emergence of LSD amidst a developing counter-cultural movement was a political event in itself—albeit one which operated along existing lines of political hierarchy and exclusion (particularly among racial lines, within and beyond the US).⁶³ Despite the universal community promised by Timothy Leary and other psychedelic “gurus” of the 1960s, it would be irresponsible not to recognize how a collective experience of spiritual elevation is tolerated by the

state for some, and prosecuted for others.⁶⁴ However, this does not mean we should discount psychedelic politics entirely, for its value emerges in the lasting changes to how we live in the world and connect with those around us long after the trip has ended. Historically, psilocybin and other psychedelics have been utilized in underground group therapy sessions and wellness retreats, but discussion of their benefits has begun to move out of therapeutic settings and into the public sphere.⁶⁵ For example, the potential benefits of incorporating psychedelics into existing climate movements was taken up by numerous groups at the annual Climate Week gathering in September of 2024, indicating that there is a popular movement looking to tap into psilocybin's political potential.⁶⁶ While some may be rightly skeptical, such movements are not without transformative potential. Lisa Sideris argues that psychedelics may offer a pathway to overcoming the alienation of the human from non-human nature, so that we might better apprehend the scale of the climate crisis through a lens of joy and passion rather than grief and nihilistic inaction.⁶⁷ Donna Haraway further articulates the political potential of Western engagement with Indigenous material practices, writing that this “experimental materialism... is not a New Age wish nor a neocolonial fantasy, but a powerful proposition for rethinking relationality, perspective, process, and reality without the dubious comforts of the oppositional categories of modern/traditional or religious/secular.”⁶⁸ Furthermore, in an era characterized by fragmented, digitally rooted relationships replete with an inundation of advertisement and information, we might see cultivating a habit of contemplative “zen” practices as a necessary political act for citizens to undertake.⁶⁹

The applications of psychedelic politics go well beyond meditative practices or peaceful interactions with non-human nature; they can even manifest in ways which directly contest the lines of exclusion that Saldanha rightly saw in 1960s counterculture movements. Leor Roseman and Nadeem Karkabi conducted field studies of ritualistic Israeli ayahuasca ceremonies in which Palestinians participated—on the condition that the ceremony remain apolitical.⁷⁰ They open with an account from Ruqaiya, an Israeli citizen of Palestinian descent, who participated in an Israeli-guided session on Yom Kippur, who saw “cycles of war, blood flowing onto the land, and mothers who sacrifice their children.”⁷¹ This violent rupture of the senses and perception, rather than facilitating unity and collectivity, led to a desire for “justice, equality, and recognition.” Ruqaiya, who had long denied her ancestry, saw herself as transformed by the experience and came away with “a new sense of mission... She became a facilitator of ayahuasca rituals that incorporate Palestinian cultural elements and political awareness into the practice.”⁷² Another Israeli-Palestinian participant, Khalil, was overcome by intense anxiety and saw a vision of an elderly Palestinian couple who were forced out of their home in an Israeli resettlement project. Amidst the despair, he found himself “born again” and “made peace with the Arab” in himself.⁷³ Even though the state can facilitate and limit the potential of a psychedelic politics as Saldanha recognizes, the seeds

of revolutionary political action can take root even amidst a barbaric, apartheid regime.

Another contemporary example can be found among the Tsleil-Waututh Nation, which is occupied by Canada and the city of Vancouver. Reuben George, a Sundance Chief, has developed psychedelic healing ceremonies to help Indigenous communities cope with the traumas of land dispossession and state violence, particularly survivors of residential schools. Yet he also seeks to expand his practice to incorporate Canadian settlers as well, to promote reconciliation and to develop better ways of living and working alongside one another to develop a brighter political future.⁷⁴ Psychedelics here allow pain and trauma to be transformed into compassion, love, and sustained interconnection, for as Reuben and Rowe note, we all carry a spirit inside of ourselves. For those of us who live in a hellish multiplicity of political crises, a taste of heaven can help us find reconnection and the will to move forward.

The intentional altering of our perceptions and rupturing ourselves from ingrained ego-centered habitus may be a discomforting task at first, but it creates space for the potential cultivation of collectively focused imagination that struggles to flourish in a political system that has left many of us in a state of alienation and despair. As challenging as this practice can be, I wish to emphasize the joy that can be realized in the moment of psychedelic experience, and the healing shifts in imagination and perspective that can prepare us to step back into the political arena and embrace those around us in solidarity. Adopting a positive spirituality, in William Connolly's words, requires deliberate attempts to alter our perceptions, for the "strain of existential gratitude already festering within and between us" can be "amplified tactically and brought to situational judgments and political actions when a new event jostles this or that chunk in the received banisters of judgment."⁷⁵ The willful engagement with aesthetic, affectively intense experience creates new conditions from which freedom from individuation can emerge as we reforge our attachments to the world surrounding us.

CONCLUSION: GROUNDING THE PSYCHEDELIC

In this essay, I have argued that the development of a psychedelic politics is an imaginative method for confronting the alienated world in which many of us find ourselves, and to counter the logics of transhumanism that seek to "liberate" us from modes of life rooted in collective engagement and corporeality. The model of psychedelic politics that I have theorized thus far has focused largely on therapeutic mindfulness practices and liberatory explorations of imagination at the individual level, so that practitioners might embrace new, radical ways of living in the world. For those who are new to the experience of psychedelics, an individual, guided experience is an ideal starting point. However, there is also value in imagining psychedelic politics as a collective experience—especially given the individuation and alienation we experience in a fragmented, digital world. James Rowe notes that integrating mind-body

practices (in various forms) with social politics is one way to alleviate existential dread and isolation, while countering the corporate sector's appropriation of mindfulness practices as a means of promoting "self-optimization and material success."⁷⁶ Christine Hauskeller makes a similar claim against psychedelic therapy as a neoliberal tool of appropriation of Indigenous cultural practices, and one which further alienates the subject by emphasizing personal productivity and self-realization at the cost of social connection.⁷⁷

This appropriation can also take place without the psychedelic agents themselves. Some researchers have developed virtual reality tools to elicit psychedelic experiences with the goal of fostering similar therapeutic outcomes; yet they fail to take into account the role of the body and the affective intensity of psychedelic experience, pursuing a "trip" in which the body plays no role—thereby rendering it a fundamentally apolitical experience.⁷⁸ Furthermore, by placing subjects in a shared physical space with headsets that replaced other bodies with "glowing lights," it effectively obscured the bodies, facial expressions, and other forms of communication that would have led to a shared therapeutic experience. Without the anxiety, awe, and elation that psilocybin and other psychedelics present, our perceptions of the world and moral judgments would likely remain static and unchanging. Embracing the intensity of such an experience and accepting the challenge to our egos can help us feel attachment not just to our bodies and sensorial experiences, but to the vitality of the world around us.

However, we can also cultivate such intense, sublime embodied experiences without turning to psychedelics. As Jason Frank argues, transformative political moments emerge when popular assemblies manifest as a form of action, one that seizes political power from representatives and returns it to a radical collective.⁷⁹ However, there is also an affective, embodied dimension to collective action: the intensity of feeling lost in the crowd as bodies are pressed against one another, the sensorial chaos of chanting and yelling, and the vulnerability and anxiety of placing oneself at risk of physical harm and incarceration from the state. Writing on the political nature of corporeality, Laura Quintana argues that the emancipation of the body (as a political individual) begins with moments of rupture and subtle displacement that impact the senses and the body's lived experiences.⁸⁰ These moments of rupture have a lasting impact, which "may lead to an imaginative reflection (a reflection that produces other images of the world) on what it is that robs bodies of their mobility, their possibility of displacement, their freedom, and their desire for a different world."⁸¹ This affectively charged, uncertain, imaginative, and collectively shared sensation is also a form of psychedelic politics.

I close with a more rejuvenating (and perhaps even joyful) example of a cultural group that embraces and emphasizes collectivity, taps into a liberatory escapism, and encourages its members to safely participate in an embodied, transcendental, and productively overwhelming psychedelic experience. In seasonal "festival" culture, tens of thousands of people gather to camp and

lose themselves in musical and artistic experiences for a weekend—with all attendees and staff tacitly recognizing that most people in attendance are on one psychedelic or another.⁸² There is a uniform atmosphere of PLUR (Peace, Love, Unity, Respect) governing the festival’s social interactions, so attendees can comfortably lose themselves in the chaotic arrhythmia of reverberating bass music, lasers, and bodies pressed against one another. There is a joy to be found in the temporary dissolution of ego and losing oneself amidst a celebratory collective.⁸³

Imagine a political theorist and junior scholar who loves the profession and academic community, but struggles with the precarity and occasional isolation that accompanies academic work. An annual experience of ego dissolution in a vast community could be seen as liberating, as well as empowering for the scholar to carry lessons from those experiences into the next year of teaching, research, and political activism. Beyond setting aside anxieties around bodily discomfort and dirtiness to embrace the sweaty mass of flesh in a mosh pit and lie on the bare earth in a forest (to “touch grass,” as the saying goes), the personal revelations of the chaotic trip persist long after the weary trudge back to daily life: Which professional goals are worth pursuing while balancing happiness; which moral relationships need to be corrected; how to recognize the goodness of others and facilitate dialogue across lines of polarization; and how best to fight for our shared future. Rupturing our perception of what is familiar allows us to imagine new possibilities for the world, and to bring forth that new world through the lessons that persist long after the moment of rupture has ended.

NOTES

1. See Elena Cristina Mitrea et al, “Extreme Pessimists? Expected Socioeconomic Downward Mobility and the Political Attitudes of Young Adults,” *Political Behavior* 43 (2021): 785-811.
2. Ben Ramanauskas, “What Transhumanism Means for Our Future,” *Oxford Political Review* (online edition), February 21, 2022. <http://oxfordpoliticalreview.com/2022/02/21/what-transhumanism-means-for-our-future/>
3. Brad Evans and Chantal Meza, “The Techno-Theodicy: How Technology Became the New Religion.” *Theory & Event* 25, no. 3 (2022): 639-664.
4. Christian P. Weber. “In Defense of Humanism: Envisioning a Posthuman Future and Its Critique in Goethe’s Faust,” In *Posthumanism in the Age of Humanism: Mind, Matter, and the Life Sciences after Kant*, eds. Edgar Landgraf, Gabriel Trop, and Leif Weatherby, 244. Weber here offers an excellent differentiation between transhumanism and other philosophical traditions in the vein of posthumanism.
5. Jodi Dean. *Solidarity of Strangers: Feminism After Identity Politics* (University of California Press, 1996), 2-3.
6. Jodi Dean, *Crowds and Party*, (Verso, 2016), 44-45; 50-55; 67-71.

7. Dean, *Crowds and Party*, 40-41.
8. Peter Bloom. *Identity, Institutions and Governance in an AI World: Transhuman Relations*. (Palgrave Macmillan, 2020), 131-172.
9. It is worth noting that there are contesting readings of posthumanist technological assemblages that, in certain settings, allow us to recover the human subject. For example, Jack Black and Jim Cherrington, in an examination of the assemblages that emerge in increasingly digitized healthcare settings, that the human subject emerges within and questions its role in a neoliberal, impersonal, political ecology of health. See: Jack Black and Jim Cherrington. "Posthuman to Inhuman: mHealth Technologies and the Digital Health Assemblage." *Theory & Event* 25, no. 4 (2022): 726-750.
10. Ramanauskas, "What Transhumanism Means for Our Future."
11. For foundational work in this tradition, see Martine Rothblatt, *Virtually human: The promise and the peril of digital immortality* (St. Martin's Press, 2014); David J. Chalmers, "Uploading: A Philosophical Analysis," in *Intelligence Unbound: The Future of Uploaded and Machine Minds* (eds. Russell Blackford and Damien Broderick) (Wiley Blackwell, 2014), 102-119.
12. James K. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness: Why Transforming Fear of Death is Politically Vital* (Routledge, 2024), 8-9; 72-75; 105-110. As an example, messianic Christian doctrines frame death as the final enemy that drives us to embrace the liberation promised in resurrection.
13. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness*, 33; 803. Rowe also does excellent work on alternative attitudes towards death and dying in Indigenous philosophy, namely among the Haudenosaunee people and Coast Salish communities.
14. Joshua Hurtado Hurtado, "Exploited in Immortality: Techno-Capitalism and Immortality Imaginaries in the Twenty-First Century," *Mortality*, October (2023): 1-18.
15. Zygmunt Bauman, "Survival as a social construct," *Theory, Culture & Society* 9, no. 1 (1992): 1-36.
16. Hurtado, "Exploited in Immortality," 18.
17. Hannah Arendt, *Lectures on Kant's Political Philosophy*, ed. Ronald Beiner (University of Chicago Press, 1992), 64-65.
18. Immanuel Kant, *Critique of Judgment*, trans. James Creed Meredith (Oxford University Press, 2007), 83-88. See also Paul Guyer, *Kant and the Experience of Freedom* (Cambridge University Press, 1993), 36-37; 98.
19. Linda M.G. Zerilli, "'We Feel Our Freedom': Imagination and Judgment in the Thought of Hannah Arendt," *Political Theory* 33 (2005): 163 (emphasis added.)

- For Zerilli's more exhaustive project on political judgment, see: Linda M.G. Zerilli, *A Democratic Theory of Judgment* (University of Chicago Press, 2016).
20. For examples of these arguments, see, for example, Patrick Riley, "Hannah Arendt on Kant, Truth, and Politics," *Political Studies* 35 (1987): 379-392; Andrew Norris, "Arendt, Kant, and the Politics of Common Sense," *Polity* 29, no. 2 (1996): 165-191; Matthew C. Weidenfeld, "Visions of Judgment: Kant, Arendt, and the Misreading of Judgment," *Political Research Quarterly* 66, no. 2 (2012): 254-266.
 21. See Paul Guyer, *Kant and the Experience of Freedom* (Cambridge University Press, 1993), 3-9; Kennan Ferguson, *The Politics of Judgment: Aesthetics, Identity, and Political Theory* (Lexington Books, 1999), 102-106.
 22. Rachel Zuckert, *Kant on Beauty and Biology: An Interpretation of the Critique of Judgment* (Cambridge University Press, 2007), 179.
 23. Zuckert, *Kant on Beauty and Biology*, 150-160.
 24. Arendt, *Lectures*, 67.
 25. Avshalom M. Schwartz, "Political imagination and its limits," *Synthese* 199 (2021): 3329-3333.
 26. Schwartz, "Political imagination," 3330.
 27. Schwartz, "Political imagination," 3333-3339. It is worth noting here that Schwartz differentiates between the creative and critical elements of imagination by noting that the critical need not necessarily be innovative but can simply be deconstructive. I do not think it is necessary to disentangle the two for as I note further down, both forms of imagination can be harnessed in order to support the status quo and inhibit the health of civil society.
 28. Schwartz, "Political imagination," 3331.
 29. Chiara Bottici, *Imaginal Politics: Images Beyond Imagination and the Imaginary* (Columbia University Press, 2014): 106-124.
 30. Schwartz, "Political imagination," 3335.
 31. The theoretical literature on awe and wonder is extensive and beyond the scope of this paper, but a contemporary and expansive overview can be found in Helen de Cruz, *Wonderstruck: How Wonder and Awe Shape the Way We Think* (Princeton University Press, 2024).
 32. Immanuel Kant, *Critique of Judgment*, 77. Similarly, British philosophers Shaftesbury and Hutcheson maintained that the viewing subject remains wholly disinterested from the experiences of nature unless objects of absolute beauty (either objects without comparison in nature or ones which are uniformly unique amidst nature's variety) independently galvanize our cognitive capacities. See Guyer, *Kant and the Experience of Freedom*, 50-61;72.

33. Kant, *Critique of Judgment*, 83-88.
34. Edmund Burke, "A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origins of Our Ideas of the Sublime and the Beautiful," in *The Portable Edmund Burke*, ed. Isaac Kramnick (Penguin Books, 1999), 64. (*italics added*)
35. Burke, "A Philosophical Inquiry," 119.
36. Burke, "A Philosophical Inquiry," 120.
37. Jeremy Bendik-Keymer, "The self-work of planetary justice," *Environmental Politics* (2023): 1; 15.
38. Arendt, *Lectures*, 43. *Emphasis added.*
39. Donna Haraway, *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene* (Duke University Press, 2016), 127.
40. John Dewey, *Art as Experience* (1934), 42; 108.
41. Ramzi Fawaz draws on a psychedelic reinvigoration of literary criticism, noting the liberatory potential of expanded imaginative capabilities, as a compelling argument for recovering the humanities in academia. See Ramzi Fawaz, "Literary Theory on Acid," *American Literary History* 34, no. 1 (2022): 126-141.
42. Michael Pollan, *How to Change Your Mind: What the New Science Teaches Us About Consciousness, Dying, Addiction, Depression, and Transcendence* (Penguin Press, 2018), 58-61; 141.
43. Brian Massumi, *Politics of Affect*, (Polity, 2015), 48-49.
44. See Torsten Passie, et al, "The Pharmacology of Psilocybin," *Addiction Biology* 7 no. 4 (2002): 357-364.
45. David B. Johnson, "The Postmodern Sublime: Presentation and Its Limits." In *The Sublime: From Antiquity to the Present*, ed. Timothy M. Costelloe, 124. See also Dewey, *Art as Experience*, 170-171.
46. Julia Kristeva, *Powers of Horror: An Essay on Abjection*, trans. Leon S. Roudiez (Columbia University Press, 1982), 15.
47. Johnson, "The Postmodern Sublime: Presentation and Its Limits," 125.
48. Dewey, *Art as Experience*, 55.
49. Dewey, *Art as Experience*, 55.
50. Michael Halewood, "Making Your Soul Visible," in *Philosophy and Psychedelics: Frameworks for Exceptional Experience* (eds. Christine Hauskeller and Peter Sjöstedt-Hughes) (Bloomsbury, 2022), 95-106.
51. Halewood, "Making Your Soul Visible," 100-101.
52. Massumi, *Politics of Affect*, 20-21.
53. Immanuel Kant. *Critique*, 76-80.

54. Pollan, *How to Change Your Mind*, 366-368; 379-380.
55. James K. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness: Why Transforming Fear of Death is Politically Vital*, 80; 85.
56. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness*, 80; 85.
57. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness*, 370-372.
58. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness*, 378-381. Emphasis added.
59. Rowe, *Radical Mindfulness*, 378-381.
60. See Matthew W. Johnson and Roland R. Griffiths, "Potential Therapeutic Effects of Psilocybin," *Neurotherapeutics* 14 (2017): 734-740; Roland R. Griffiths et al, "Psilocybin Can Occasion Mystical-Type Experiences Having Substantial and Sustained Personal Meaning and Spiritual Significance," *Psychopharmacology* 187 (2006): 268-283.
61. Matthew M. Nour et al, "Psychedelics, Personality, and Political Perspectives," *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs* 49, no. 3 (2017): 182-191.
62. Kant, *Critique*, 85-88.
63. For examples of these tensions in the US and India, see Arun Saldanha. "The LSD-event: Badiou not on acid," *Theory and Event* 10, no. 4 (2007); Saldanha, "Music, Space, Identity: Geographies of Youth Culture in Bangalore," *Cultural Studies* 16, no. 3 (2010): 337-350.
64. The considerable police presence at music festivals in the United States is a perfect example of this tension.
65. As some states have pursued legalization measures for psilocybin, clinical guided therapies have become accessible in Oregon, Colorado, and California. More states are likely to join that list in the near future through ballot initiatives, and across the country there are "underground" therapy sessions led by licensed mental health clinicians. These sessions are surprisingly easy to locate for those interested in performing their own research on the topic.
66. Dharna Noor and Oliver Milman, "Trip on psychedelics, save the planet: the offbeat solution to the climate crisis," *The Guardian* (October 2, 2024). <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2024/oct/02/drugs-climate-crisis>.
67. Lisa H. Sideris, "Radical Strategies: Cultivating Eco-Consciousness Through Wonder and Psychedelic Experience," *Journal for the Study of Radicalism* 17, no. 2 (2023): 149-177.
68. Donna Haraway. *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*, 165.
69. Shannon Mariotti, "Zen and the Art of Democracy: Contemplative Practice as Ordinary Political Theory," *Political Theory* 48, no. 4 (2020): 469-495.

70. Leor Roseman and Nadeem Karkabi, "On Revelations and Revolutions: Drinking Ayahuasca Among Palestinians Under Israeli Occupation," *Frontiers in Psychology* 12, no. 7 (2021).
71. Roseman and Karkabi, "On Revelations and Revolutions," 1-2.
72. Roseman and Karkabi, "On Revelations and Revolutions," 1-2.
73. Roseman and Karkabi, "On Revelations and Revolutions," 6-7.
74. James K. Rowe, "Meet the Indigenous leader using psychedelic medicine to heal the traumas of colonization," *Waging Nonviolence* (November 25, 2024). Rowe also talks about his own experience in one of these reconciliation ceremonies, and I strongly encourage readers to read this article in greater detail. <https://wagingnonviolence.org/2024/11/indigenous-leader-reuben-george-heal-traumas-colonization-psychedelic-medicine/>
75. William Connolly, *Facing the Planetary: Entangled Humanism and the Politics of Swarming* (Duke University Press, 2017), 59.
76. Rowe. *Radical Mindfulness*, 12-13. Another example of this appropriation is the language of "manifesting" one's material desires and drives into action, commonly used by social media influencers.
77. Christine Hauskeller, "Individualization and Alienation: Paradoxes in Psychedelic Psychotherapy," in *Philosophy and Psychedelics: Frameworks for Exceptional Experience*, 107-132. I have a number of criticisms of this particular argument, which others fantastically articulate in this response article: Julien Tempone-Wiltshire and Traill Dowie, "Psychedelics and critical theory: A response to Hauskeller's individualization and alienation in psychedelic psychotherapy," *Journal of Psychedelic Studies* 7, no. 3 (2023): 161-173.
78. David R. Glowacki et al, "Group VR experiences can produce ego attenuation and connectedness comparable to psychedelics," *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 8995 (2022).
79. Jason Frank, *The Democratic Sublime: On Aesthetics and Popular Assembly* (Oxford University Press, 2021).
80. Laura Quintana, "Jacques Rancière and the emancipation of bodies," *Philosophy and Social Criticism* 45, no. 2 (2019): 218-219.
81. Quintana, "Jacques Rancière...'," :218-219. Quintana is not speaking of psychedelics here, but the necessity of affective physical sensation and its role in generating a reflective imagination is in line with how a psychedelic politics functions, as I have theorized it. Her work is a helpful way to theorize the links between corporeality and political action.
82. It is important to quickly mention that not all psychedelics are created equal. LSD and psilocybin operate in ways that are different from ketamine and MDMA with somewhat different effects, but all are both prevalent in both recreational

and therapeutic settings. See Rachel Nuwer, *I Feel Love: MDMA and the Quest for Connection in a Fractured World* (Bloomsbury, 2023).

83. For those interested in an excellent sociological study of this topic, see Robin Sylvan, *Trance Formation: The Spiritual and Religious Dimensions of Global Rave Culture* (Routledge, 2013).